

SABILULUNGAN AS A TOURISM DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IN RURAL COMMUNITIES

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Abstract

Tourism is one of the new style industries that are able to provide rapid economic growth in terms of employment, income, living standards and in activating other production sectors within the receiving country.. Indonesia has applied the strategy of optimization and development of tourism sector. Optimizing rural areas into a tourism sector in Indonesia is a concept of rural areas development that called as a tourism village. The uniqueness of the strategy that undertaken by the village community in Indonesia that is located in West Java in the development of tourism sector is known as the concept of "sabilulungan". Sabilulungan is a Sundanese word that means gotong royong or cooperate. Sabilulungan itself can be used as a strategy in optimizing and developing tourism villages in West Java. The uniqueness of Sabilulungan or cooperation on the positive value of society where the previous concept that Geertz proposed on the concept of cooperation in the Java community is interpreted as a form that is defined as sharing the poverty cake. Sabilulungan is used as a tourism village development strategy implemented in West Java, a case study that researchers found in Kampung Ciseupang, Nagrog Village, Cicalengka District, Bandung Regency.

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1. Introduction

Archipelagic countries become Indonesian identity as a country. The existence of Indonesian islands is spread from Sabang to Merauke which consists of 17,500 islands with a coastline of about 95,181 km.¹ (Kusmana & Himat, 2015). Indonesia as an archipelagic country certainly has various kinds of diversity, among these diversity consists of the diversity of flora, fauna, and culture and ethnicity.

The diversity of cultures and ethnic groups or often referred to as ethnicity in Indonesia is illustrated by the slogan of "Bhinneka Tunggal Ika" which means different but still one. Ethnic or ethnic diversity is evidenced by the presence of a large number of ethnic groups, cultures, religions, and others that are each plural (plural) and at the same time heterogeneous.² (Lestari, 2015). Indonesia's diversity is spread evenly across various islands in Indonesia. One of the diversity of cultures and ethnic groups with the existence of ethnic groups namely ethnic Sundanese.

Ethnic Sundanese is one ethnic group that has a large enough population. According to data on ethnic distribution in Indonesia, the number of ethnic Sundanese populations in Indonesia is 30 million. The size of the distribution of tribes in Indonesia places the Sundanese ethnic as the second largest ethnic group in Indonesia.³ (Pitoyo & Triwahyudi, 2017). According

to Kontjaraningrat (2004), what is referred to as Sundanese or Ethnic Sundanese are people who for generations use Sundanese language and dialect as mother tongue and dialect in everyday conversation.⁴ Most of the Sundanese ethnic distribution in Indonesia is in the West Java region.

Ethnic Sundanese existence in West Java is often found to live in groups in the same area. Sundanese ethnicity is an ethnic group that holds strong traditions and various kinds of cultural practices in the past that are universal, one of which is sabilulungan or what can be called mutual cooperation.

Sabilulungan is currently a government program. Sabilulungan is a word taken from Sundanese and has the meaning of picking up nurture, taking care, caring, penance, patience, and faith which all contribute to forming a society that has a character and high work ethic to maintain its culture. (Sutarman, 2017).⁵

This study was conducted to explain that there is another potential for the implementation of sabilulungan as a strategy that can be applied by the community in increasing tourism potential in the village. This research was conducted in Nagrog Village, Bandung Regency, West Java.

2. Methods

The method used in the study is a qualitative approach with a case study research design. Case studies are used as a design in research that is used to see various cases that occur, specifically to compare between cases and where researchers conduct in-depth analysis of the case (Creswell, 2017).⁶ Data collection in this study was conducted by interview, observation, and secondary data retrieval in the form of archives from Nagrog Village. The sampling method in this study was conducted by purposive sampling method. Purposive sampling is a method of sampling by selecting specifically people who are able to provide information clearly in accordance with the questions and objectives needed by the researcher so that the required information will not be obtained through other informants (Maxwell, 2013).⁷ The informants from this study were residents of Ciseupang Village, traditional leaders, religious leaders, and community leaders in Ciseupang Village, Nagrog Village, Bandung Regency, West Java Province. The analysis carried out is by reducing the data, displaying data, and summarizing the findings data from the field derived from the informant categories (Miles & Huberman, 1994).⁸ This research was conducted in Ciseupang Village, Nagrog Village, Bandung Regency, West Java Province

3. Result and Discussion

The Profile of Desa Nagrog

Nagrog Village is a village located in the District of Cicalengka, Bandung Regency, West Java Province. This village has an area of 417.16 ha with the following usage division :

Table 1. Data on the use of Nagrog Village area

Use of Area	Area
Rice field area	120,00 ha
Dry land area	280,36 ha
Wet land area	0,00 ha
Plantation land area	0,00 ha
General facilities area	8,80 ha

Forest area 8,00 ha

This village is divided into five hamlets with a population of 16,108 people. The following is the distribution of population data in Nagrog Village :

Table 1. Data the distribution of the population of Nagrog Village

Hamlet Name	Amount of RT	Amount of KK	Souls	Man	Woman
I	18	1.181	3.771	1.895	1.876
II	18	1.328	4.330	2.217	2.113
III	17	1.080	3.323	1.697	1.626
IV	10	655	2.113	1.072	1.041
V	12	785	2.571	1.298	1.273
Total		5.029	16.108	8.179	7.929

The main livelihood owned by Nagrog Village residents is generally farm laborers. As many as 742 people of Nagrog Village worked as farm laborers while 219 people worked as Civil Servants.

Tourism Village Development Potential in Nagrog Village

One of the potential possessed by Nagrog Village is the potential in the forestry sector. Nagrog Village has an area of 8.00 ha with an altitude of 700 meters above sea level. The potential of forestry in the Nagrog Village area includes the presence of one type of local plants typical of the region that fall into the category of rare plants. The plant is named Warulot Tree. Other forestry potentials are the beauty of the landscape and the location of forests in the highlands that are able to serve the beauty of the Nagrog Crossing.

In 2017, the Bandung Regency Environmental Service initiated a program called Taman Kehati. Taman Kehati is an environment-based tourism village development project. Among the 16 regions nominated as the construction site for the Taman Kehati, Ciseupang Village located in Bandung Regency was chosen as one of the two Taman Kehati construction sites carried out in Bandung Regency.

In Taman Kehati, which was built in Ciseupang Village, hundreds of different types of trees will be planted from the village. One of the unique plants owned by Ciseupang Village is Warulot Tree, which is a tree that has two colors of flowers and from a distance looks like a twinkling lamp. In addition, various types of animals such as eagles, some primates, and freshwater shrimp will be bred there. The Taman Kehati project aims to boost the economy of the surrounding community and become a means of educational tourism.

Sabilulungan in the Development Process in Ciseupang Village

One of the philosophy of life that develops in Sundanese culture is to pick up teasers, take compassion, take care. Picking up has an understanding as the nature of giving knowledge to one another to encourage individual capacity building in mastering science. Compassion has meaning as a nature that loves one another and helps one another to help people in need. Foster care has meaning as a trait to guide one another to continue to apply positive values in life and avoid negative values.

The three values are incorporated in the concept of sabilulungan value. Sabilulungan contains the value of unity, helping each other and working together in community life. This sabilulungan value is still closely linked to the people living in Ciseupang Village and is reflected in the Taman Kehati development program. Some of the factors that encourage this sabilulungan value to develop in the life of the Ciseupang Village people in Nagrog Village are:

Kinship System and historical similarity.

Relatives have two definitions, namely broad understanding and narrow understanding. The term relative is broad, as said by Suyono and Siregar in Jamaludin (2015), referring to people who live in the same or near areas. While narrowly speaking, the term kin is given to people who are bound by marital relationships or descent relationships. Ciseupang villagers have the same ancestral background that is from Hj. Mama Dasuki who is a religious leader who spread Islam in the area of Ciseupang Village, Nagrog Village, Bandung Regency. The second generation of these descendants is Ki Yoyo who is the son of Hj. Mama Dasuki. The third generation, Ibu Oon, was followed by a fourth generation led by Mr. Faisal as a community figure. The existence of the Ciseupang Village community who still have the same lineage causes the importance of helping in daily life.

Religion

Ciseupang village is a whole village of various Islamic communities. The similarity of religion and belief reinforces the existence of mutual help.

“Sami-sami Umat Islam mah kan kedah silih bantosan, Rasul ge jelas atos marentahkeun yen unggal muslim teh duduluran. Komo urang didieu rata-rata sadayana masih keluarga”

With this statement, it proves that being a strong factor in the existence of mutual cooperation or mutual cooperation that is developed in the community and maintained and applied for generations. The sabilulungan value is not only applied to fellow citizens but also applied in the form of joint government development. In the construction process, Taman Kehati was built with a bottom up and top down system that complemented each other.

Sabilulungan between the Bandung Regency government and the residents of Ciseupang Village

The Bandung Regency Government is aware of the importance of the value of mutual cooperation or community cooperation in the field of development. Therefore, the Bandung Regency government also promotes Sabilulungan as a development motto in Bandung Regency. By implementing the Sabiluungan value in the development process, finally the Bandung Regency government can improve the human performance index (HDI) for the past six years (republika.co.id). Likewise in the construction of Taman Kehati in Ciseupang Village; The government cooperates with the people of Ciseupang Village, represented by community leaders, one of them is the Chairperson of Gapoktan (Joint Farmers Group). Through representatives of community leaders, the community expressed their aspirations regarding the development of Taman Kehati. In addition to conveying aspirations, the participation of the community of Ciseupang Village in the development of Taman Kehati also took place in the monitoring of the Taman Kehati development process.

Sabilulungan as a Development Effort

Geertz in his book entitled *Agricultural Involution* (1963) states that the concept of "togetherness" which is owned by the Indonesian people, especially the Javanese people, brings the community into the distribution of poverty. Geertz calls this concept the concept of shared of poverty. In the facts on the ground that occurred in Kampung Ciseupang, a culture of togetherness or sabilulungan did not bring people into poverty, but the culture of togetherness brought people to advance through development.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Sabilulungan is a regional government program. Basically, sabilulungan does not only function as a value that has been passed down through generations in the Sundanese ethnic community. However, sabilulungan can also be used as a strategy for developing tourism in the ethnic Sundanese community. Therefore, the government should be able to pay attention to the importance of embedded cultural values, so that it can be used as a concrete strategy in increasing tourism potential in Indonesia.

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